

Unilateral Parotitis Secondary to Flupenthixol Decanoate in a Schizophrenia Patient: A Very Rare Side Effect

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Thioxanthene class, particularly flupenthixol is not yet an established cause of parotitis, a rare side effect of anti-psychotics. However, the risk of parotitis is still possible due to its anticholinergic property.

Results: We reported a case of flupenthixol decanoate-induced parotitis with xerostomia. According to the parotitis-specific criteria Modified Naranjo Probability Scale, flupenthixol decanoate is a probable cause of parotitis in this patient.

Conclusion: Correct identification of flupenthixol as the responsible agent for anticholinergic-induced parotitis is the most pivotal step to treat the parotitis and prevent recurrence.

KEY WORDS

flupenthixol decanoate, parotitis, xerostomia, anticholinergic

INTRODUCTION

Both physical and mental health do play an integral part of mentally disordered patient in ensuring a quality life. Antipsychotic drugs are unarguably crucial in improving the quality of life of psychiatric patient but the various types of devastating physical side effects are notable¹⁾. Among the worth mentioning side effect of antipsychotic is parotitis. There are scores of reports regarding drug-induced parotitis in the field of medicine. Antipsychotics have been established as a cause, most notably clozapine as well as the first generation antipsychotics from the phenothiazines class. However, the incidence remains unknown because of the rarity²⁾. Up to date, flupenthixol decanoate of the thioxanthene class has never been associated with parotitis. Nevertheless, it is possible in view of the anticholinergic, antidopaminergic and antiserotonergic properties exerted by this drug^{3,4)}. Typically the parotitis abated with the termination of the offending agent²⁾.

CASE REPORT

A recently discharged 59-year-old man with paranoid schizophrenia was referred to otorhinolaryngology specialist for progressive painful right parotid swelling of two days duration. It was preceded by the frequent dry throat after the initiation of antipsychotic treatment a few months before. Otherwise, there was no fever, sore throat, toothache, earache, and scalp infection or recent history of trauma or insect bite.

Intramuscular flupenthixol decanoate treatment was started 12 weeks ago with the last dose at 60 mg given eight weeks ago. The patient was admitted to the psychiatric ward after he developed anticholinergic-induced delirium superimposed on severe cognitive deficit secondary to flupenthixol decanoate. Since then he was not given any other antipsychotics or anticholinergic medication.

On examination, the patient was comfortable and hydration was fair.

There was trismus about two finger breadths. The right parotid swelling measured 4 x 3 cm, erythematous, warmth and tender on palpation. Intraoral examination showed no pus at the right Stensen's duct upon milking the right parotid gland. The dental hygiene was good but the mucosa appeared dry. Flexible nasopharyngolaryngoscopy revealed no significant finding at nasopharynx, oropharynx, hypopharynx and larynx. During the referral, he was not delirious with Elderly Cognitive Assessment Questionnaire (E-CAQ) score of 8/11 indicating a cognitive deficit. This was an improvement over previous ECAQ score of 2/11 during the psychiatric admission.

White cell count $8.89 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, eosinophil count $0.04 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ and serum electrolytes were within normal range. Neck ultrasonography revealed an enlarged with heterogenous hypoechoic area within measuring 1.5 x 8.1 cm. There was no evidence of liquefied component. The left parotid gland was normal. In sum, this finding was suggestive of right acute parotitis. The parotitis-specific criteria Modified Naranjo Probability Scale score was seven.

He was encouraged to increase his oral intake to avoid dehydration. Sialogogue was prescribed to promote salivation. Intravenous amoxicil-

Figure 1. Ultrasonography of neck demonstrated enlarged and heterogenous hypoechoic area of right parotitis

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lin clavulanate 1.2 g and metronidazole 500mg, thrice daily were empirically given. After five days, his condition greatly improved and was discharged well.

At one week follow up, the parotid swelling had subsided and the ECAQ score had returned to a perfect score of 11. At three months follow up, there was no recurrence of parotid swelling. He was later started on sulpiride without any similar complication.

DISCUSSION

Flupenthixol decanoate is a long-acting depot of thioxanthene class. With a half-life of 17 days, the washout period following repeated intramuscular injections is estimated to be at least three months³. This long half-life ensures compliancy but at the disadvantage of prolonged side effect. Therefore, it is of no surprise that the parotitis developed during the second month after the last flupenthixol decanoate injection. The flupenthixol decanoate was a probable cause of this patient's parotitis based on parotitis-specific criteria Modified Naranjo Probability Scale².

In a review, three possible mechanisms were suggested. The first was allergic reaction that resulted in parotid swelling and skin rashes, the second was hypersalivation which is commonly related to clozapine and bilateral painless parotid swelling, and the third was hyposalivation associated with xerostomia due to antimuscarinic effect, especially in situations where patients have poor dental hygiene which may predispose to infection².

Flupenthixol may induce parotitis through the disruption of salivary gland in producing and secreting adequate saliva. Reduced saliva production gave rise to xerostomia which leads to parotitis. In contrast to other major salivary glands, the susceptibility of parotid gland derived from the fact that it is mainly composed of serous acini responsible in producing thin watery secretion. Any decrement in body fluid homeostasis such as dehydration may lead to reduce salivary flow function⁵. Besides, salivation involves a complex mechanism dependent upon the parasympathetic, sympathetic, dopamine, and serotonin activation^{3,6}. In this case, it is postulated that reduced saliva production was mainly by the peripheral anticholinergic effects of flupenthixol^{3,4}.

Interestingly, the temporal relationship between the central anticholinergic effects of flupenthixol decanoate was also evidenced through the low ECAQ score. The ECAQ score was 2/11 while the patient was warded due to anticholinergic-induced delirium, then the ECAQ score of 8/11 while having parotitis, and lastly a perfect score a week later after discharge. At this time, the parotitis had resolved. It is possible that the patient was very sensitive to central and peripheral anticholinergic effects of flupenthixol manifesting as delirium and parotitis, respective-

ly. It is crucial to identify the anticholinergic agent such as flupenthixol as the offending cause so that parotitis can be prevented in the future by administration of antipsychotic without anticholinergic property such as sulpiride³

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Flupenthixol decanoate may induce parotitis in a susceptible patient. Psychiatrist should always be vigilant of the potential risk factors and eventually prevent this complication by ensuring the patient to have adequate hydration and good oral hygiene. The cessations of the offending medication and initiation of antipsychotic without anticholinergic property ensure successful treatment to prevent further recurrence. Multidisciplinary management of drug-induced parotitis by psychiatry and otorhinolaryngology doctors is recommended.

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